

Proceedings of the “Think Tank Hackathon”, Big Data Training School for Life Sciences Follow-up, Ljubljana 6th – 7th February 2018

Sabrina Schulze¹, Živa Ramšak², Yen Hoang³, Eftim Zdravevski⁴, Juliane Pfeil⁵, Ariel Duarte-López⁶, Uwe Baier⁷, Maja Zagorščak²

1 Cell2Fab (Synthetic Biology, Faculty of Biochemistry and Biology), University of Potsdam, Potsdam, Germany

2 Department of Biotechnology and Systems Biology, National Institute of Biology, Ljubljana, Slovenia

3 Department of Signal Transduction, German Rheumatism Research Center Berlin, A Leibniz Institute, Berlin, Germany

4 Department of Information Systems, Faculty of Computer Science and Engineering, Sts. Cyril and Methodius University, Skopje, Macedonia

5 Division Molecular Biotechnology and Functional Genomics, Technical University of Applied Sciences, Wildau, Germany

6 DAMA-UPC, Department of Computer Architecture, Technical University of Catalonia, Spain

7 Institute of Theoretical Computer Science, Ulm University, Ulm, Germany

Abstract

On 6th and 7th February 2018 a Think Tank took place in Ljubljana, Slovenia. It was a follow-up of the “Big Data Training School for Life Sciences” in Uppsala, Sweden, in September 2017 and was focused on optimizing the program for the forthcoming “Advanced Big Data Training School for Life Sciences”, under the patronage of the COST Action CHARME (Harmonising standardisation strategies to increase efficiency and competitiveness of European life-science research - CA15110). The aim of the Think Tank was to go into details into several topics that were - to a degree - covered by the preceding training school. Likewise, discussions embraced recent experience of the attendees in light of the new knowledge obtained by the training school and how it comes into perspective into their current and upcoming work. The attendees were also responsible for identifying topics of interest for a follow-up training school later in 2018. The 2018 training school should strive for and further facilitate optimized applications of Big Data technologies in life sciences. This workshop was fully organized by the attendees of this hackathon.

Background and course

In September 2017 the first “Big Data Training School for Life Sciences”¹ was organized by EU COST Action CHARME² and EMBnet³ and took place in Uppsala, Sweden (Pfeil *et al.*, 2018a). Although the academic background of young bioinformaticians participating in this training school was somewhat diverse, we all came to conclusion that it is a necessity to learn more about handling Big Data in life sciences. It was denoted how it would be a great deal if additional useful topics could have been demonstrated, with ones already presented in Uppsala shown in more detail. Out of these constructive discussions the idea of additional training came up and it was proposed to the members of CHARME and EMBnet. This idea was welcomed with interest and approved in the form of the short

¹ <http://astrocyte.com/COST-CHARME/COST-CHARME/Home.html>

² www.cost-charme.eu

³ www.embnet.org

pre-meeting, which was organized by the participants themselves. As a result, the Think Tank hackathon⁴ was organized at the Medical Faculty of the University of Ljubljana⁵, Slovenia on 6th and 7th February, 2018 with the support of ELIXIR Slovenia⁶.

The hackathon was only open to attendees of the original training school in Uppsala, with eight of them enthusiastically participating (Figure 1). The organisation of this event was done under the leadership of Maja Zagorščak and Živa Ramšak, with supplementary help of all the other attendees. As all the participants share the trait **“don't just tell me how to do it, I want to really figure it out”**, the main focus of the meeting was the exchange of substantial knowledge about top level technologies and *in situ* troubleshooting by solving some real problems.

Prior to the training school, with the help of a questionnaire regarding group expertise and interests and taking advantage of various collaboration technologies (e.g. Slack, GitHub and Dropbox), we identified and agreed on several feasible topics, such as **“Code, Parallelize, Containerise!”**, **“Image analysis with OpenCV - from leaf shape to chords”**, **“Machine learning - do it yourself”** and **“Deep learning without a PhD”**.

The attendees, each knowledgeable in their subfield, took complementary lead on diverse topics and were solely responsible for preparing presentation materials, code examples and tasks for the hackathon. During the two days, all topics were covered by active participation of all attendees. Additionally, we brainstormed (hence the name Think Tank) and wrote a preliminary report about a potential advanced training school.

Figure 1. Attendees of the Hackathon joined by COST Action CHARME and ELIXIR.si representatives (image by Sabrina Schulze).

The first day was opened by Maja Zagorščak with some introductory words about workshop goals, organization and schedule. Her introduction was followed by Eftim Zdravevski, on the topic of Docker technology and its Big Data applications. He discussed parallelization using Apache Spark™ (Zaharia *et al.*, 2010) and demonstrated k-means clustering and classification examples using the MLLIB

⁴ <http://conferences.nib.si/BigData/>
<http://cost-charme.eu/events/follow-up-training-school>

⁵ <http://www.mf.uni-lj.si/en/index.html>

⁶ <https://www.elixir-europe.org/about-us/who-we-are/nodes/slovenia>

(Meng *et al.*, 2016), Spark's scalable machine learning library. Hence, he guided us through the process of algorithm parallelisation using the data-parallel computing paradigm, while discussing its performance and computational acceleration, using an approach similar to the ones presented in (Zdravevski *et al.*, 2015a; Zdravevski *et al.*, 2015b). The second part of the day was filled by Juliane Pfeil with a lecture on OpenCV, a computer vision library. She guided us through basic concepts of image analysis (i. e. noise reduction, segmentation, structural pattern recognition and prediction) and demonstrated which functions and parameters are optimal for specific predetermined tasks (for an example see Pfeil *et al.*, 2018b). Lastly, she showed an interesting example on how detection of the center of mass and radial function application can be used to transform bioimages into chords. All source code developed during the Think Tank hackathon is available online at GitHub repository Big Data Think Tank⁷.

The second day began with “**Deep learning without a PhD**”, where Yen Hoang introduced Google’s TensorFlow open-source library, which among others is also used for machine learning applications (e.g. neural networks). She guided us through various detailed presentations by Martin Görner (GitHub repository: TensorFlow MNIST Tutorial⁸) and moderated the discussion about neural network theory and the underlying code to increase our comprehension. For this section, the entire infrastructure was setup in advance by ELIXIR.si member Andrej Kaštrin (users, applications, dependencies), which resulted in no time loss for the participants once the workshop started. Additionally, this led into an informal discussion over Docker usability in R, to ease issues with transparent data sourcing, availability and traceability of published results. These concerns are also of vital importance considering principles of FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable) scientific data management (Wilkinson *et al.*, 2016). The presentations were concluded by an impromptu presentation given by Uwe Baier, regarding his ongoing work in data compression with examples, among them the magic of the Burrows–Wheeler transform (BWT; Baier *et al.*, 2016). Aside from standard BWT application in text compression, it was shown advantageous in many NGS alignment algorithms in the context of memory reduction.

Both days were rounded off by discussions and brainstorming sessions regarding the organisation and structure of a potential follow-up training school to be organised later in 2018. A possible organising committee, suitable dates and location of the training school were discussed; these will be formulated into an official proposal, which is not a part of this paper. The Advanced Big Data Training School for Life Sciences was proposed to last 5 days, with various topics suggested to be focused on: feature extraction, deep learning with both free of charge and payable software tools and platforms (e. g. services offered by Microsoft Azure) or the backbone computational infrastructure required for tasks in Big Data analysis. All of these topics represent attractive options, given the current developments in these fields, especially if the knowledge learned is connected to real-world problems, which the participants of this Think Tank will attempt to organise far in advance of the Advanced Training School. It was also agreed to invite experts on these topics, which would explain the theory behind these applications and assist during the practical parts of the workshop. These ideas were finalized on the evening of the second day, where preliminary time slots were agreed upon, including time for theory sessions and practical parts. The majority of practical sessions are proposed to be group tasks, where the participants would jointly work on some pre-selected datasets. The results of these practical sessions would then be presented to the remaining groups, thus optimizing the time constraints of such tasks, while at the same time allowing for continual growth via collaboration of the participants. On that note, social activities were also taken into account in the schedule, again fostering future cooperation of participants. We finally decided that participants of the previous one should be preferred as attendees for the advanced training school. The remaining slots will be filled by further applicants, provided they are eligible given their background.

⁷ <https://github.com/zagorGit/BigDataThinkTank>

⁸ <https://github.com/martin-gorner/tensorflow-mnist-tutorial>

At the end of the Think Tank, a biweekly journal club was proposed where related papers will be read beforehand and discussed in the one hour session. In the beginning, this should be held only with the participants of the Uppsala training school. After some routine, collaborators could join to the video conference via Skype or similar. This club would allow a progressive alignment of the participants' level regarding machine learning and deep learning elements.

Figure 2. The attendees during the deep learning session (image by Sabrina Schulze).

Summary

This Think Tank event turned out into two interesting and productive days. We established the knowledge base on four different topics and identified topics for a possible advanced Big Data training school. The attendees who gave presentations on the hackathon noticed how it is sometimes easier to suggest improvements than to apply them in practice, however the intellectual freedom in organisation gave us the opportunity to think outside the box. We consider the results of these days as a useful starting point leading towards a proposal for the Advanced Training School. Additionally, the idea of a biweekly journal club would help to bring all participants on the same level and to strengthen the network.

Fortunately, there was also some moderate time scheduled for social events and networking. One was on the evening before the first session, where we spent some time playing abstract games in a board-game tavern, thus getting acquainted with other participants mindsets in a relaxed and casual manner. This idea was well accepted, hence we suggest that it should also be scheduled in other follow-up events - it offers a good opportunity of catching up or getting to know potential new participants better. The other social event on the evening of the first day, a dinner with CHARME WG5 representatives, helped set up foundations for some future collaborations and ideas on how to get the wheels in motion with the organisation of the Advanced Training School. We decided to try (maybe even on a boat).

Acknowledgement

We would like to thank ELIXIR.si for allocating rooms for us at the University of Ljubljana (Faculty of Medicine) and for infrastructural support. Further thanks for COST Action CHARME for providing

us with the necessary funding for this event (COST Action CA15110 is supported by the EU framework program H2020). A special note of acknowledgement and gratitude goes to Maja Zagorščak and Živa Ramšak for preparing the collaboration tools and environments, the schedule and leading the organization of the event in the highest of standards.

References

1. Baier U, Beller T, Ohlebusch E (2016) Graphical pan-genome analysis with compressed suffix trees and the Burrows–Wheeler transform, *Bioinformatics*, Volume 32, Issue 4, Pages 497–504, <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btv603>
2. Meng X, Bradley J, Yavuz B, Sparks E, Venkataraman S, Liu D, Freeman J, Tsai DB, Amde M, Owen S, Xin D (2016) Mllib: Machine learning in apache spark. *The Journal of Machine Learning Research*, 17(1), pp. 235-1241.
3. Pfeil J, Schulze SK, Zdravevski E, Hoang Y (2018a) Report on the “Big Data Training School for Life Sciences”, 18-22 September 2017, Uppsala, Sweden. *EMBnet journal* 23.
4. Pfeil J, Frohme M, Schulze K (2018b). Mobile Microscopy and Automated Image Analysis: The ease of cell counting and classification. *Optik & Photonik*. 13. 36-39. 0.1002/opph.201800002.
5. Wilkinson MD, Dumontier M, Aalbersberg IJ, Appleton G, Axton M, Baak A, Blomberg N, Boiten JW, da Silva Santos LB, Bourne PE, Bouwman J, Brookes AJ, Clark T, Crosas M, Dillo I, Dumon O, Edmunds S, Evelo CT, Finkers R, Gonzalez-Beltran A, Gray AJG, Groth P, Goble C, Grethe JS, Heringa J, 't Hoen PAC, Hooft R, Kuhn T, Kok R, Kok J, Lusher SJ, Martone ME, Mons A, Packer AL, Persson B, Rocca-Serra P, Roos M, van Schaik R, Sansone SA, Schultes E, Sengstag T, Slater T, Strawn G, Swertz MA, Thompson M, van der Lei J, van Mulligen E, Velterop J, Waagmeester A, Wittenburg P, Wolstencroft K, Zhao J, Mons B (2016) The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific Data*, 3, 160018. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>
6. Zaharia M, Chowdhury M, Franklin MJ, Shenker S, Stoica I (2010) Spark: Cluster computing with working sets. *HotCloud*, 10(10-10), p. 95.
7. Zdravevski E, Lameski P, Kulakov A, Jakimovski B, Filiposka S and Trajanov D (2015a) Feature ranking based on information gain for large classification problems with mapreduce. In *Trustcom/BigDataSE/ISPA, 2015 IEEE* (Vol. 2, pp. 186-191). IEEE.
8. Zdravevski E, Lameski P, Kulakov A, Filiposka S, Trajanov D and Jakimovski B (2015b) Parallel computation of information gain using Hadoop and MapReduce. In *Computer Science and Information Systems (FedCSIS), 2015 Federated Conference on* (pp. 181-192). IEEE.